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Transformational leadership style of Supervisors/Heads as Perceived by the Employees and the attitude of employees toward the School

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Abstract. The study intended to determine the effect of the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads toward the attitude of employees to the school. To carry out the study, the related literature was reviewed to strengthen the theory of the study. The population of the study was all employees of the two colleges in the two provinces. It used questionnaires to gather the data and used a descriptive correlational research design. The weighted mean was used to determine the transformational leadership and attitude level and the Pearson r or Product Moment of Correlation was used to determine the correlation between transformational leadership style and the attitude of employees toward the school. The study found that there is a significant correlation between the two variables and therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Keywords. transformational leadership, idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, cognitive, affective, conative attitude

I. Introduction/ Rationale

I have been conducting several studies related to attitude and behavior and the context of my studies have been the Divine Word Colleges. The studies focused on finding the correlation between the attitude and behavior of a person. These studies used the theory of Ajzen (1985, 1987) and Allport (1935) of attitude and behavior. Their theories argued that attitude influences or affect the behavior of a person or in short, attitude is a key predictor of behavior (Thomas & Znaniecki, 1918, Watson, 1925). However, the result of the previous studies had produced mixed results. Several studies confirmed the theory of Ajzen (1985, 1987, & 1993) and Allport (1968) but some results proved otherwise, that there is no correlation. For example, Abun (2019) conducted a study on the correlation between the attitude of students toward research and their behavioral intention to research in the future found a correlation. The same finding was also found when it came to attitude toward the Catholic Church and the behavioral intention of students to help the Church in the future. The study found a correlation. But there was a different result when it came to the attitude of students toward corruption and their behavioral intention to corrupt. The finding showed that there was no correlation. The finding indicated that though the students have the knowledge and certain feeling about corruption but such attitude has nothing to do with corruption. This finding triggered more queries in my mind

about other factors that cause corrupt behavior. The researcher found an answer that the social environment can be a determining factor for the behavior of the person. This answer is supported by previous findings of other early researches such as De Fleur & Westie, (1958) and Deutscher, (1969). They suggested that instead of studying the relationship between attitude and behavior, the researchers should study the social context and norms as a determinant factor in predicting behavior or human action.

Based on the recommendation of De Fleur & Westie, (1958) and Deutscher, (1969), the current study tries to reverse the ordinary theory which emphasized the influence of attitude toward behavior but the influence of social environment toward the attitude of the person. The researcher believes that attitude is formed by the culture or the practices of a particular place (Abun, 2018, Donald, 2002, & Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995). In line with such a concept, the current study would like to investigate leadership practice or leadership styles of school supervisors/heads and the affective attitude of employees toward the school/institution. There have been no studies similar to this topic and the researcher feels it important to conduct the study to find out if leadership practice influences the attitude of employees toward the school. The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction in which it discusses the rationale or the background of the study and the objective of the study. The second part is the review of related literature and studies that discusses the basic concept of the study. The third part is the research methodology. It discusses the research design, locale of the study, the population of the study, research instruments, and the statistical treatment of the study. The fourth part is the empirical data and analysis in which it presents the empirical data and its analysis. The fifth part is the results and discussion that discusses the result of the study which leads to its conclusion.

II. Literature Review

This is a review from previous research and discussion on the topic to provide a theoretical foundation of the study (Machi & McEvoy, 2016). Thus, this part discusses the different concepts of leadership and transformational leadership from different authorities and field studies related to transformational leadership.

The Concept of Leadership

It cannot be denied that there are many different kinds of the definition of leadership, however, they have a common core concept of leadership that leadership is about relationship and influence. For example, Bennis and Nanus (2007) define leadership as a process by which a leader induces his/her followers to behave in a desired manner. Similar to that idea, Hollander and Julian (1969) view leadership as the presence of a particular influence of the relationship between two or more persons. Even Rauch and Behling (1984) consider leadership as a process of influencing an organized group toward attaining pre-determined objectives. On the other hand, leadership is also about the relationship. Influence does not exist in a vacuum but in a relationship. Thus, Merton (1969), Hogan, and Curphy (1994) looked at leadership as an interpersonal relation in which others comply because they want to, not because they have to. While Bass (1998), Tichy and Devanna (1986) view leadership as an effort to transform followers and create a vision to be attained and articulate a vision and ways to attain the vision. Without elaborating more on other opinions on leadership, based on the above definitions we have the idea of several important aspects of leadership which are interpersonal relationship, influence, and goals. Leadership exists in the realm of relationship and it is one of his/her functions to create a community and building a good relationship between him/her and followers. Without it, leadership does not work (Schaefer, 2015). It helps to make the leader

effective (Riggio, 2014). Beyond creating a good relationship, a leader should be able to influence his followers to follow him/her. Thus, there is a power to affect others (Goncalves, 2013). Lastly, a leader has a goal to achieve. The purpose of creating good relationships and exercise influence over followers is to attain organizational goals (Gartenstein, 2018).

Transformational Leadership Style

Transformational leadership is an approach that focuses on the change in individuals and the social system. In other words, it creates a valuable and positive change in the followers or in short to change followers into leaders. Burns (1978) introduced the concept of transformational leadership. It is not a set of specific behavior but it is a process in which leaders and followers raise one another to a higher level of morality and motivation. In the exercise of leadership, a leader should appeal to higher ideals and moral values such as justice and equality. In support of Burns' view, Bass (1985) argued that transformational leaders motivate their followers by appealing strong motivation toward the need or demand of potential followers. They look for potential motives in followers and seek to satisfy their higher needs such as self-actualization and engage the full person of the follower, not only intellectually but also morally. They try to uplift people into their better self as a person. For Burns (1978) the essence of transformational leadership is in its effort to establish a good relationship between leaders and followers particularly when leaders and followers are engaging each to a higher level of motivation and morality. Leaders derive genuine satisfaction from helping their followers to grow and therefore they take personal interest to help their employees to grow through activities that enhance their development, not only in terms of skills, knowledge but also morally.

Transformational leaders do not focus too much on the weakness of employees but they focus on the potential of the employees on what they can do and contribute to the organization. They do not focus on the past of the employees but focus on the growth of the employees because they believe that they can change. In this case, they see their employees in terms of actuality and potentiality. They confirm the individuals on what they are and what they can be. Helping their employees to realize their potentials is their primary concern because they are fully aware that it is through employees, the objectives of the company can be attained. To do that a leader needs to inspire their employees, secure their cooperation, create confidence, provide a working climate, motivate them to work more, provide guidance and direction and create a team spirit (Pratigma, n.d). In short, leaders engage in the full person of the followers. Employees are not just means to an end but they are ends in himself or herself and therefore employees' engagement in the whole process of management is necessary.

Elements of Transformational Leadership

The original author of transformational leadership is Burns and Bass. Originally, Burns (1978) was interested in the moral aspect of leadership. While Bass (1990) is concerned about its efficacy, particularly on how a leader influences his followers. According to Bass, followers look up to their leader because of their charisma and because they trust the leader and thus Bass identified dimensions of transformational leadership such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Clayton, 2016 cited from Bass, 1985, Wodehouse, 2015, Riggio, 2014, Schieltz, 2019).

Idealized influence

The first element of transformational leadership is the idealized influence. It refers to a leader's capability to influence the behavior of his/her followers by being a role model to them (Zdaniuk & Bobocel, 2015). In this case, a leader does not use power and authority to influence his/her

followers to follow him but simply by living his values and doing himself what he/she demands from his/her followers. In other words, he/she walks the talk (Riggio, 2014). It is the leaders' personality that matters. The followers are convinced to follow the leader when they see his/her honesty and truthfulness to what he/she is saying and doing. The behavior of a leader instills pride in followers and becoming proud to be associated with the leader (Hughes, 2014). He/she is motivating his/her followers through his/her willingness to take a risk in whatever circumstance and does not abandon his/her values or principles under any situation he/she is in. It is through his/her actions that build trust and confidence in his/her followers (Schieltz, 2019).

Inspirational motivation

The first element focuses on the moral aspect of leadership. The second element emphasizes its efficacy. It is about the leader's ability to inspire followers' confidence, motivation, and a sense of purpose. He/she inspires his/her employees or followers not only by his/her skills or knowledge but through his/her self-confidence to carry out the vision and mission of the company and he/she projects such self-confidence through articulating a clear vision for the future, communicate expectations for the group and demonstrate confidence and commitment to attain the goals (Wodehouse, 2018) and whatever it takes. Therefore, inspirational motivation is not about telling people to accept things as they are but to dare one's self and employees or followers to take the risk in accepting change and facing challenges because only through it can transcend themselves. However, these identified risks and challenges can motivate followers or employees if these risks or challenges are connected to their heart or concern that they care about. Challenging the followers to go higher is one of the leader's function.

Intellectual stimulation

The third element of transformational leadership is intellectual stimulation. This element requires a leader to involve the followers in generating ideas and decision making. He/she fosters and develops his/her team through questioning and encourage the team to question the status quo. In other words, the leader invites them to be creative, innovative, and make decisions out of the box (Belmejdoub, 2015, Riggio, 2014, Schieltz, 2019, & Hill, 2013). This kind of leadership style will broaden the mind of followers to see problems from different perspectives and consequently enrich the followers' knowledge to carry out their duties and responsibilities. Followers are encouraged to take a different path or method in solving problems. Most importantly, by involving followers in solving organizational problems, the followers feel that they are part of and own the organization and the problems in it.

Individualized consideration

This element demands that a leader cannot treat their employees or followers the same. Employees have different needs and capabilities, skills, and knowledge. Thus, a leader needs to consider individual employees' needs and provides the necessary training that suits their needs and desires (Yeap, n.d). In this case, the leader has a piece of knowledge about individual employees and develops a supportive relationship, and offers help to develop the employees according to his/her needs. He/she shows genuine concern for the needs and feelings of employees and offers support to help the employees (Belmejdoub, 2015). The purpose of this kind of person is to bring out the best in the employees (Riggio, 2014).

The Influence of Transformational leadership on Job satisfaction, effectiveness, and Performance of teachers

Studies have been conducted to measure the correlation between different leadership styles and how different leadership styles correlate to different outcomes. For example, Shin (2013) conducted a study to determine the effect of transactional leadership and laissez-faire leadership styles and organizational commitment. He found that transactional leadership styles positively correlated to organizational commitment, while the laissez-faire leadership style is negatively correlated to organizational commitment. Basit (2018) also performed a study on the effect of democratic, laissez-faire, and autocratic leadership styles. His study found that the democratic leadership style has the most significant influence on the work performance of employees and followed by the laissez-faire leadership style. While autocratic leadership style is poorly correlated to employee performance. These findings indicate that exercising a certain leadership style can bring some impact on the performance of employees, whether it is positive or negative. Particularly transformational leadership styles have been studied by many researchers and the studies found that transformational leadership style is correlated to job satisfaction, extra effort, and effectiveness (Nidadhavolu, 2018). As Elmore (2004) also pointed out in his study that applying transformational leadership styles such as participation in decision making produces a climate of collegiality and collaboration, in which the school community embraces a shared vision and shared commitment to school change. It promotes interpersonal relationships and foster communication (Bass, 1985). Such an environment can boost morale and performance of every member of the community and consequently it enhances the job satisfaction of teachers (Korkmaz, 2007) and improve school climate. This is found by Friedman (2004) too that transformational leadership changes the workplace culture and productivity by appealing to high ideals, by changing assumptions, and by building commitment to common goals and objectives. Therefore, Demir, (2008) emphasized that applying transformational leadership styles in the school setting is important to promote school development. It supplies a link to teacher outcomes and teacher beliefs regarding their individual and collective ability in addition to their collective capacity.

Theories on Human Attitude

In the current concept of human attitude, the researcher follows his previous argument that he has presented and published in different international journals related to a similar topic on human attitude and human behavior. This part is using the same references because the researcher believes that they are the authority when it comes to a discussion on how human attitude affects behavior. The readers expect to encounter similar presentations of ideas with the researcher's previous presentation in other papers.

Attitude is an individual's disposition to react to a certain object, person, institution, event, or other discriminable aspects of the individual's world (Ajzen, 1993, cited by Abun, 2018). Ajzen argued that there are a lot of definitions of attitude from different theorists, however, there is a common agreement among them that attitude has its evaluative dimension (Bem, 1970, Edwards, 1957, Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In the sense that dimensions of attitude can be measured and evaluated. Though the attitude is hidden because it is in the mind of the person but it can be measured through the reaction or responses of the person toward the object of the attitude which may be favorable or unfavorable toward the object, persons, institution, events, or situations. There are three categories of responses or reactions toward an object or person or an institution and they are *cognitive response, affective and conative responses* (Allport, 1954, Hilgard, 1980, Rosenberg & Hovland, 1960). These are manifestations of salient or latent attitude which is unobservable (Ajzen, 1993). *The cognitive component* refers to the beliefs

and thoughts about the subject, the object, the person, the institution, the event, etc. It is about the perception and information of the person toward the subject, object, or person. **The affective component** of attitude is an emotional reaction toward the subject, object, or person. It is how one feels when he/she is confronting the subject, object, the person, or the institution. It is still a psychological reaction which may be a verbal or nonverbal expression of feelings toward the subject, object, the person, or the institution. Such a reaction may be negative or positive. While the **conative component** of attitude is the effect of the attitudes toward a behavioral intention or how the attitude toward the object, the person affects one's behavior. These may include plans, intentions, and commitments to a planned behavior. These are the three components of attitude and therefore, attitude is a multidimensional construct.

The question can be raised concerning the origin of attitude: where does it come from? According to Ajzen (1993), a person develops such an attitude perhaps as a result of watching television programs or maybe other kinds of exposures or experiences. But Abun (2017) went deeper to answer that question concerning his argument on how to solve an environmental problem. According to him, that environmental problem is a result of human behavior, and destructive human behavior is originated from the culture and thus solving the environmental problem is to revisit the culture that has influenced the mind of people toward the environment. He contends that attitude is originated from the culture where the person is raised. His argument was based on the ideas of anthropologists such as Donald (2002), Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995). Donald (2002) argued that culture is playing an important role in our brain functioning and even brain structure. She has pointed out that language has the biggest impact on brain structure but that culture influences brain functioning to a great extent as she writes:

The social environment includes many factors that impinge on development, from bonding and competitive stress to the social facilitation of learning. These can affect brain functioning in many ways, but usually, they have no direct influence on functional brain architecture. However, symbolizing cultures own a direct path into our brains and affect the way major parts of the executive brain become wired up during development. This is the key idea behind the notion of deep enculturation... This process entails setting up the very complex hierarchies of cognitive demons (automatic programs) that ultimately establish the possibility of new forms of thought. Culture effectively wires up functional subsystems in the brain that would not otherwise exist.

The idea of culture and its effect on brain functioning indicates the power of culture over the formation of the mind and ideas of people about everything around them (Abun, 2018). Donald's View is similar to what Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995) as he argued that culture is the collective programming of the human mind that distinguishes the members of one human group from those of another. Hofstede pointed out clearly that that culture is reflected in how people think, how people view things, or attitude. To elaborate on the idea of Hofstede, Armstrong (1996) contend that there is a relationship between cultural dimensions and ethical perceptions. In other words, an ethical attitude is formed by a particular culture. One perceives a certain object, subject, person, or institution to be negative or positive, favorable or not favorable because he/she has been taught by the culture of a particular society where he/she is living. What he/she learns from the culture will be his/her ideas about a certain subject, object or events, etc. that he/she will encounter.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Source: National Library of Medicine (n.d).

Figure 1: Presents the independent and dependent variables of the study. It projects the influence of the independent variables toward the dependent variables (National Library of Medicine, n.d). In this study, Transformational leadership styles stand as independent variables and the cognitive and affective attitude of employees or faculty toward the school stands as dependent variables.

Statement of the Problems

The study plans to investigate the correlation between transformational leadership styles and the attitude of faculty of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, specifically to answer the following questions:

1. What is the transformational leadership styles of the administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:
 - a. Idealized influence
 - b. Inspirational motivation
 - c. Intellectual stimulation
 - d. Individualized consideration
2. What is the attitude of employees toward the school in terms of
 - a. cognitive attitude
 - b. the affective attitude
 - c. conative attitude
3. Is there a relationship between transformational leadership styles and attitudes of employees toward the school?
- 4.

Assumption

The study assumes that the consistent practice of certain leadership styles of administrators can affect the attitude of faculty toward the institution.

Hypothesis

The study relies on the theory of Donald (2002), Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995). Donald and Hofstede argued that culture is playing an important role in our brain functioning and even brain structure. Their ideas indicate the power of culture over the formation of the mind and ideas of people about everything around them (Abun, 2018). Base on this theory, the study hypothesizes that leadership practices affect the cognitive, affective, and conative attitudes of employees toward the school.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study covers only the employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region and it limits its investigation only to four dimensions of transformational leadership styles and its influence on the cognitive and affective attitude of the employee toward the school. The limitation of the study is that it covers only Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region and therefore, it may not represent all the Divine Word Colleges in Northern Luzon.

III. Research Methodology

The study is carried out through appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Since the study is quantitative research and therefore it used descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research to determine the level of transformational leadership styles of leaders/managers and its correlation with the cognitive and affective attitude toward the institution. The nature of descriptive research is to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and statistical treatment. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situation, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes “what is” about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

In line with the current study, the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational method were deployed. The study determines the level of transformational leadership styles and their effect on the attitude of faculty toward the school. This was to determine what the dominant transformational leadership styles of leader or manager were and to what extent it affects the attitude of faculty and employees toward the institution.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees and faculty of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The total enumeration sampling was used and 250 faculty and employees were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adapted validated questionnaires of Multifactor Leadership Questionnaires (MLQ) that were made by Avolio, et.al (1995) and cognitive and affective and conative attitude questionnaires were made by the researcher based on the main concept of attitude and behavior correlation of Ajzen (1993) and went through content validity by the experts.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the President of the Colleges, requesting them to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college. The researcher personally met the Presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President's representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the college.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In consistence with the study as descriptive research, therefore descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of transformational leadership styles of leaders/managers and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of transformational leadership styles toward the cognitive and affective attitude of faculty and employees toward the school.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

IV. Empirical Data and Analysis

Empirical data and analysis are evidence-based approach research. The approach is based on the empirical data that are gathered through research instruments such as questionnaires or interviews (Angelov, et.al., 2016). Based on this concept, this part presents the data that was gathered through questionnaires and have been tabulated statistically. The arrangement of the presentation is following the statement of the problem of the study.

Problem1: What is the transformational leadership styles of the administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of:

- a. Idealized influence
- b. Inspirational motivation
- c. Intellectual stimulation
- d. Individualized consideration

Table 1a. Transformational Leadership Styles of the supervisors/heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region as to Idealized Influence.

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Display conviction to the vision and mission of the College.	3.45	A
2. Act in ways that build the respect of employees/subordinates.	3.34	SWA
3. Emphasize the importance of purpose, commitment, and ethical consequences of decisions.	3.33	SWA
4. Display the most important values such as honesty, integrity, justice, transparency, and consistency.	3.20	SWA
5. Go beyond self-interest for the good of the college.	3.30	SWA
Composite Mean	3.32	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

As indicated in table 1a, it shows that as a whole, the leadership style of supervisors/heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of idealized influence gained a composite mean of 3.32 which is interpreted as "somewhat agree or Moderate". This confirms that their transformational leadership style along with idealized influence is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. Even when the items are taken singly, almost all of the items have the same level of interpretation, "somewhat agree or moderate" particularly "acting in ways that build the respect of employees/subordinates (3.34), emphasizing the importance of purpose, commitment, and ethical consequences of decisions (3.33), displaying the most important values of honesty, integrity, justice, transparency, and consistency (3.20), going beyond self-interest for the good of the college (3.30) and only one was evaluated high such as displaying conviction to the vision and mission of the College" (3.45).

The evaluation alarms the school administrators of the leadership problem. It reminds the administrators to revisit their transformational leadership styles particularly along with idealized influence and to improve it.

Table 1b: Transformational Leadership Styles of the Administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region as to Inspirational Motivation.

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Articulate a compelling vision/goals of the future.	3.32	SWA
2. Challenge employees/subordinates with a high standard of performance.	3.28	SWA
3. Provide encouragement and moral support for the employees/subordinates.	3.18	SWA
4. Inspire the employees/subordinates through his passion and determination to achieve the goals.	3.23	SWA
5. Inspire employees/subordinates to see the priorities in carrying out their duties and responsibilities.	3.23	SWA
Composite Mean	3.25	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Following the idealized influence is inspirational motivation. The data reveals that as a whole, the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads in terms of inspirational motivation obtained a composite mean of 3.25 which can be understood as "somewhat agree or moderate level". This is also pointing out a clear picture of their leadership style, that their leadership style in terms of inspirational motivation is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. Again it displays the same concern on transformational leadership style along with inspirational motivation. Taking the items separately, it also demonstrates the same level of

assessment such as "articulating a compelling vision/goals of the future (3.32), challenging employees/subordinates with a high standard of performance (3.28), providing encouragement and moral support for the employees/subordinates (3.18), inspiring the employees/subordinates through his passion and determination to achieve the goals (3.23), inspiring employees/subordinates to see the priorities in carrying out their duties and responsibilities" (3.23).

The assessment again demonstrates a problem along with the transformational leadership style of supervisors in terms of their capability to inspire their followers or employees to go higher. It is a call to re-evaluate their leadership style and improve.

Table 1c: Transformational Leadership Styles of the Administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region as to Intellectual Stimulation.

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Question old assumptions, traditions, and beliefs.	3.21	SWA
2. Instill new perspectives and ways of doing things.	3.24	SWA
3. Encourage the free expression of ideas and reasons.	3.17	SWA
4. See different perspectives when solving problems.	3.18	SWA
5. Encourage problem-solving using reasoning and evidence, rather than unsupported opinion.	3.17	SWA
Composite Mean	3.19	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

The findings of the previous dimensions of transformational leadership styles are the same as the finding of a transformational leadership style along with intellectual stimulation. The table manifests that the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads a long intellectual stimulation reaches a composite mean of 3.19 which can be translated as "somewhat agree or moderate level". Again, the evaluation confirms the fact that the leadership style of supervisors/heads along intellectual stimulation is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. This is again confirming the previous dimensions that there is a problem of transformational leadership in terms of intellectual stimulation. Even when the items are taken singly, it still shows that all items have the same level of evaluation, "somewhat agree or moderate level" such as "questioning old assumptions, tradition, and beliefs (3.21), instilling new perspectives and ways of doing things (3.24), encouraging the free expression of ideas and reasons (3.17), seeing different perspectives when solving problems (3.18), and encouraging problem-solving using reasoning and evidence, rather than unsupported opinion (3.17).

Basing on this evaluation, it indicates a problem of transformational leadership in terms of intellectual stimulation. In other words, the supervisors need to involve the faculty or employees in solving the problems of the school and the problems must be discussed with the employees.

Table 1d: Transformational Leadership Styles of the Administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region as to Individualized Consideration

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Deal with employees/subordinates as individual persons.	3.22	SWA
2. Help individual employees/subordinates to develop their capabilities.	3.27	SWA
3. Provide training and development activities or seminars according to the needs of different employees/subordinates.	3.25	SWA
4. Are sensitive to individual differences and approach employees/ subordinates according to their traits	3.13	SWA
5. Treat employees/subordinates as individuals with different needs, abilities, and aspirations rather than just a member of the group.	3.18	SWA
Composite Mean	3.21	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

The fourth dimension of transformational leadership style is individualized consideration. As gleaned from the table, it reveals that as a whole, the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads as to individualized consideration garnered a composite mean of 3.21 which can be translated as "somewhat agree or moderate level". It concludes that transformational leadership styles of supervisors or heads along individualized consideration are not high or very high and it is also low or very low. Even when the questions are taken separately, the data reveals that all have the same level of assessment, "somewhat agree or moderate level" such as "dealing with employees/subordinates as individual persons (3,22), helping individual employee/subordinate to develop their capabilities 93.27), providing training and development activities or seminar according to the needs of different employees/subordinates (3.25), treating employees/subordinates as individuals with different needs, abilities, and aspirations rather than just member of the group (3.18) and are sensitive to individual differences and approach employees/ subordinates according to their traits(3.13).

Looking at the data, they remind the administrators/supervisors/heads of the institution to continue to revisit their leadership style or approach to employees. There is a need to treat the employees individually, not to generalize the employees.

Table 1d: Summary of Transformational Leadership Styles

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. Idealized Influence	3.32	SWA
2. Inspirational Motivation	3.25	SWA
3. Intellectual Stimulation	3.19	SWA
4. Individualized Consideration	3.21	SWA
Overall Mean	3.24	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In summary, the table shows that overall the transformational leadership styles of supervisors/heads gained a composite mean of 3,24 which means “somewhat agree or moderate level”. This concludes that the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. Taking them separately, they all have the same evaluation within the level of "somewhat agree or moderate level" such as idealized influence (3.32), inspirational motivation (3.25), intellectual stimulation (3.19), and individualized consideration (3.21).

The evaluation displays a need to continue to improve the transformational leadership styles of the supervisors along those four dimensions. Failing to improve their leadership style can affect other aspects of the organization.

- 2. Problem2: What is the attitude of employees toward the school in terms of**
- a. cognitive attitude*
 - b. the affective attitude*
 - c. conative attitude*

Table 2a: The Attitude of Employees toward the School as to Cognitive Attitude

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I know well about the school.	3.58	A
2. I know the vision and mission of the school.	3.77	A
3. I know the objectives of the school.	3.66	A
4. I know the problems of the school.	3.49	A
5. I know the strength and its weaknesses.	3.44	A
6. I know its main business.	3.58	A
7. I know the school is a Catholic school.	3.97	A
8. I know the school is centering on values formation.	3.77	A
9. I know the school is the instrument of evangelization.	3.79	A
10. I know the school is educating future Christian leaders.	3.75	A
Composite Mean	3.68	A

Source: Ajzen (1993).

Legend

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Problem number 2 of the study is measuring the attitude of employees toward the school. The first concern is related to the attitude of employees toward the school in terms of cognitive

attitude. The table demonstrates that as a whole, the cognitive attitude of employees toward the school gained a composite mean of 3.68 which means "agree or high". It just indicates their knowledge about the school is high but not very high" and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. Taking the questions separately, they all have the same level of assessment, "agree or high". They know well about the school (3.58), the vision-mission of the school (3.77), the objectives of the school (3.66), the problems of the school (3.49), the strength and its weaknesses (3.44), its main business (3.58), the school is a Catholic school 93.97), the school is centering on the values formation (3.77), the school is the instrument of evangelization (3.79), the school is educating future Christian leaders (3.75).

The result of the evaluation indicates that employees as a whole know their school and the management should capitalize on their knowledge to improve the situation of the school.

Table 2b: The Attitude of Employees toward the School as to Affective Attitude

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I love the school.	3.80	A
2. I am proud to belong to the school.	3.82	A
3. I am happy to be identified with the school.	3.75	A
4. I feel that the school is my home.	3.69	A
5. I am energized to do what I can to help the school.	3.67	A
6. I feel good if I can contribute something good to the school.	3.77	A
7. I feel good to be in school.	3.72	A
8. I feel sad when I hear something bad about the school.	3.80	A
9. I feel happy when outsiders talk something good about the school.	3.85	A
10. I am worried when the school encounters problems.	3.71	A
Composite Mean	3.76	A

Source: Ajzen (1993).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Even in terms of affective attitude, the table manifests that as a whole, the affective attitude of employees toward the school garnered a composite mean of 3.76 which translates into "agree or high". This indicates that their affective attitude toward the school is high but not very high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. It demonstrates a good sign that the employees have an emotional attachment to the school such as "they love the school (3.80), are proud to belong to the school (3.82), happy to be identified with the school (3.75), feel that the school is their home (3.69), are energized to do what they can to help the school (3.67), feel good if they can contribute something good for the school (3.77), feel good to be in the school (3.72), feel sad when they hear something bad about the school (3.80), feel happy when outsiders talk something good about the school (3.85) and are worried when the school encounters problems 93.71).

This evaluation points to a fact that as a whole, employees are emotionally attached to the school and identified themselves with the school.

Table 2c: The Attitude of Employees toward the School as to Conative Attitude

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I want to do something to help the school.	3.77	A
2. I want to contribute something good to the school.	3.77	A
3. I have to make sacrifices to help the school.	3.70	A
4. I want to promote the school to outsiders.	3.76	A
5. I do not want to contribute problems to the school.	3.80	A
6. I will always live the values promoted by the school.	3.78	A
7. I protect the name of the school.	3.84	A
8. I try to maintain a clean and green environment of the school.	3.86	A
9. I want to help the management if I can.	3.77	A
10. I volunteer to give ideas to the management.	3.75	A
Composite Mean	3.78	A

Source: Ajzen (1993).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In terms of their conative attitude, the data shows that as a whole, the behavior or the conative attitude of employees gained a composite mean of 3.78 which means that employees agree to all issues raised in the questions. It concludes that the conative attitude of employees is high but not very high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This means that the employees agree to do something to help the school (3.77), contribute something good for the school (3.77), make sacrifices to help the school (3.70), promote the school to the outsiders (3.78), not to contribute problems to the school (3.80), live the values promoted by the school (3.84), protect the name of the school (3.84), maintain the clean and green environment of the school (3.86), help the management if they can (3.77), volunteer to give ideas to the management (3.75).

Table 2d: Summary of Attitude of Employees toward the School

ITEMS	Mean	DR
Cognitive Attitude	3.68	A
Affective Attitude	3.76	A
Conative Attitude	3.78	A
Overall Mean	3.74	A

Source: Ajzen (1993).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In summary, the data demonstrate that as a whole, the attitude of employees toward the school is high (3.77). Even if they are taken separately, they all have the same level of evaluation such as cognitive attitude 93.68), affective attitude 93.76) and conative attitude (3.78).

Problem3: Is there a relationship between transformational leadership styles and attitudes of employees toward the school?

Table3: Relationship between Transformational leadership styles and Attitudes of Employees toward the School

		Cognitive Attitude	Affective Attitude	Conative Attitude
Idealized Influence	Pearson Correlation	.454**	.482**	.462**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	240	240	240
Inspirational Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.469**	.472**	.476**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	240	240	240
Intellectual stimulation	Pearson Correlation	.480**	.464**	.478**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	240	240	240
Individualized Consideration	Pearson Correlation	.491**	.483**	.507**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	240	240	240

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson r computation reveals that there is a significant relationship between the transformational leadership style and the attitude of employees toward the school at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). All dimensions of transformational leadership such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration correlate to all dimensions of attitude such as cognitive, affective, and conative attitude toward the school. It concludes that changing leadership styles can affect the attitude of employees toward the school. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

V. Result and Discussion

The study was intended to determine the effect of transformational leadership styles of supervisors or heads toward the attitude of employees to the school. The results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. Such a result demonstrates the importance of transformational leadership toward an attitude change of employees. Practicing transformational leadership styles such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration can enhance the attitude of employees in terms of their knowledge (cognitive) about the schools and its purpose and operations, their affection toward the school by which the employees become more identified with the school and love their school, their conative (behavior) toward the school as a result of their knowledge and affection toward the school. Employees' knowledge and affection toward the school translate into their behavior, particularly how they are going to help and improve the school. The results of this study display a fact that the transformational leadership style of the supervisors needs to be improved along the four dimensions of transformational leadership styles. Failing to improve their leadership styles can create a negative impact on the attitude of employees toward the school. A negative attitude toward the school can destroy the name of the school, the quality, and their work performance.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the transformational leadership style of supervisors/heads is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low but at a moderate level. Such results point out the need to improve their transformational leadership style to improve the attitude of employees toward the school and their work. The employees' attitude is high which means that employees have an idea about their school, love their school, and want to do something to help the school. Results also show that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership style and the attitude of employees toward the school. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted. The transformational leadership style affects the attitude of employees toward the school.

The researcher recognizes the limitation of the study, that the study covers only transformational leadership styles besides other leadership styles and the study also is limited to the colleges within the Ilocos Region (two provinces: Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte) and therefore may not be necessarily representing the whole Divine Word Colleges in Region I, Philippines. It is necessary to conduct another study on other leadership styles and may include a wider scope of coverage.

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